

D7.1 - Strategic Plan for the PIPs

Linking and cooperating with other projects, initiatives and policymakers

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List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package
PIP	Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers

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Abstract

Work Package 7 intends to enhance the cooperation at EU level by linking Climate Farm Demo with relevant EU Projects, Flagship Initiatives and EU Policymakers and creating synergies by organizing and facilitating meetings, workshops, webinars and other activities and events. Additionally, having the goal of strengthening national networks to contribute to the sustainability after the project has ended, Work Package 7 aims to help National Coordinators to establish links within their own country with national policymakers, national projects and initiatives, creating awareness about the project within their country and including them whenever it is relevant.

This Strategic Plan aims to plan and organize the work to be developed in these networks for the next six years, either at European or at national level. It describes the process of shaping these links, organizing and coordinating activities, collaborating with Climate Smart Advisors. Finally, it describes the process of monitoring the success of this WP, and how can we assess its outcomes and impact to the transition to more resilient farming systems using Climate Smart Farming.

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter includes an introduction to the Climate Farm Demo Project and to Work Package 7, highlighting the goals and added value of collaborating beyond CFD's network when tackling complex challenges like Climate Change. Additionally, it introduces who will be involved in this work package, either as responsible or as a target group for synergies.

Introduction

1.1. About Climate Farm Demo

1.1.1 Brief description and objectives

Climate Farm Demo is a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers (PDFs) covering 27 countries and all pedo-climatic areas. CFD will “strengthen European farmers’ capacities to implement, demonstrate and uptake Climate Smart Farming (CSF) practice across the EU and reduce their GHG emissions by 35% along the project life thus contributing to achieve the EU 2030 Climate Target Plan which aims to be carbon neutral. Therefore, Climate Farm Demo overall aims to:

first (1) **network Pilot-Demo-Farmers (PDFs)** to boost climate smart farming knowledge exchange and cross fertilisation among agricultural sectors and EU and national Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS),

then (2) **support and advise Pilot-Demo-Farmers in implementing and demonstrating the Climate Smart Farming practices** to increase innovation uptake and support the widest possible dissemination.

and finally, (3) to **incentivise the adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices across Europe** thanks to standardized methodologies and relevant rewarding mechanisms that will support farmers in their systemic transition.”

To reach this objective, the project adopts a multi-actor approach by connecting 1500 Pilot Demo Farmers and their Climate Farm Advisors (CFAs) at European and national levels to increase knowledge exchange & cross-fertilisation in their respective AKIS. The CFA’s will support the PDFs in implementing Adaptation and Mitigation Measures suggested by contextualised guidelines and will assess & monitor their environmental performance thanks to harmonised methodologies & tools.

1.2. Work package 7

Work Package 7 aims to increase cooperation beyond the project's network, by linking Climate Farm Demo to other projects, flagship initiatives and policymakers (addressed as PIPs from now on).

Figure 1 - Work Package 7 added value, contributors and target groups.

The 7th objective of the Grant Agreement is “to build a network of (i) related EU projects, (ii) Flagship EU initiatives and (iii) Policy makers (at EU and national levels) to:

1. Give visibility to the project.
2. Create cooperation.
3. Integrate research and knowledge from other projects.
4. Produce common policy and operational recommendations.
5. Prepare a sustainability strategy for the whole Climate Farm Demo network.

The Plan designed by WP7 to shape synergies both at EU level and at national level, has been based according to these established goals.

According to the Grant Agreement, the means of verification will be the exploitation of the project results/outputs in other projects and policies' recommendations, and integration of other projects' results in Climate Farm demo activities. However, WP7 will add other means of verification further described in Chapter 7.

1.2.1. Work Package 7 PIP Network

The designed network, presented in Figure 2, aims to **establish the framework Work Package 7** will work on since it goes beyond the Climate Farm Demo’s network. WP7’s main contributors from inside the CFD network will be thematic leaders, national coordinators and work package leaders.

Figure 2 - CFD and PIP Network - Main contributors of WP7

1.2.2. Responsibilities within WP7 and CFD consortium

1.2.2.1 Role of WP7 partners

WP7 partners will organize and coordinate the activities between Climate Farm Demo and the PIPs chosen – whether in project meetings, organized workshops, online webinars, among others, developing synergies at EU-level.

TEAGASC will focus on the coordination of EU projects, IFOAM and Climate-KIC will address flagship initiatives and ELO will coordinate activities with policymakers.

The synergies will not be developed by the organization of activities alone, but also by other strategies such as the dissemination of outputs and results – further developed on section **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** – as well as cooperation between the interested parties. These synergies are intended to be shaped for the seven years of the project, if found relevant: starting by WP7’s contact but continuing with the collaboration of concerning partners (further described on section 1.15).

1.2.2.2 Role of Climate Farm Demo's partners

1. Contributing to Inventory of Projects, Flagship Initiatives and Policymakers

The main priority when identifying PIPs to synergy with will be the relevance of that synergy for Climate Farm Demo. Therefore, WP7 will ask Work Package Leaders, National Coordinators and Thematic Leaders to identify PIPs and explain their relevance for their work/responsibility.

2. Contributing to the organization and planning of synergies

Climate Farm Demo's partners will give input either on their Work Packages or Thematic Area's needs or on the work already developed within CFD. By identifying specific needs or barriers in the early stage, as well as results and successful activities in later stages, the partners will help WP7 to better adapt the activities regarding the project's needs and results.

WP7 will count on the inputs of Work Package Leaders, Thematic Leaders and National Coordinators, collected through surveys and small interviews organized by CONSULAI on Climate Farm Demo's 1st year. If considered necessary, the survey will be resent in the 4th or 5th year.

3. Actively participating in the activities and events of WP7

Besides being involved in the initial planning phase of WP7, by contributing to the identification of PIPs that should be indirectly involved in the project, CFD partners will also be invited to collaborate in WP7's activities.

To ensure the activities can actively address Climate Farm Demo needs and priorities, concerned partners will be involved in the activity's development – planning, execution and evaluation.

4. Contribute to follow-up and monitoring.

Follow up activities will be encouraged by WP7 members; however these are conditioned by CFD partners and PIPs involved contributions.

Additionally, given that synergies might happen without involving WP7 members – if CFD partners directly contact PIPs – it is within their responsibility to report these synergies to this WP. To ease in this process, WP7 will draft a monitoring survey and share it regularly within the ExCom meetings.

1.3. Purpose of the Strategic Plan

The Strategic Plan aims to draft a six-year plan with guidelines for the synergy's development. By describing the type of activities, the PIPs that CFD will synergize with and the expected outcomes of these synergies, this deliverable will be an adaptable guideline for members of Work Package 7.

This plan will be adapted throughout CFD's development according to its needs and emerging opportunities – and it will serve as a living document throughout the project's lifecycle. Each year, WP7 will revise the types of activities to be developed, the KPIs established, the metrics to evaluate, etc. and will adapt whatever is found necessary.

1.4. Target PIPs

This Work Package's target groups are both within the Climate Farm Demo's Project and beyond its network. Although Work Package Leaders, Thematic Leaders and National Coordinators will be the main target groups within the network that WP7 will focus on, every partner on Climate Farm Demo should benefit from these synergies.

Additionally, there are 3 key target groups beyond CFD's network: **Projects, Flagship Initiatives and Policymakers**. WP7 will focus on specific goals and messages according to each PIP and will therefore establish different strategies for collaboration.

1.4.1. Definition of the target PIPs

EU and National Projects

An EU project is a collaborative project funded by the European Union, that addresses specific challenges, promote cooperation and achieve common objectives among EU member states and, in some cases, associated countries. Whereas a national project is a comprehensive and focused project undertaken by a specific country to advance scientific knowledge, technology development or creative solutions within a particular sector. National projects typically involve significant financial investments, which can be a combination of public and private funding (government funding, grants and subsidies, public-private partnerships, etc).

These projects encompass a wide range of sectors, such as research and innovation, environmental protection, social inclusion and economic growth. EU projects aim to foster EU integration, knowledge sharing and the development of solutions that benefit both the participating countries and the broader EU community.

The outcomes of such projects often contribute to the development of new technologies, products and policies with the potential to benefit society and economy.

Flagship Initiatives

A flagship initiative is a high impact and strategic program or project, often initiated by a government, organization or institution, designed to address a specific challenge or achieve a significant goal. These initiatives typically represent a focal point of efforts, often involving substantial resources, expertise and collaboration, to drive innovation, research and policy actions in critical areas, such as climate change.

Policymakers

A policymaker is an individual or entity responsible for creating, implementing and influencing government policies. Policymakers can operate at various levels of government – from local and regional authorities to national and international institutions. Their primary role is to make decisions that shape public policy, which in turn can impact various aspects of society, including economics, education, healthcare, environmental regulations, and more.

1.4.2. Added value based on target audience

EU Projects and Flagship Initiatives: The intention of synergies with projects and flagship initiatives will be to create cooperation and accelerate exchange knowledge between different AKIS actors involved in PIPs through facilitated discussion, organized workshops and other activities named in section 4.

This cooperation intends to:

- Disseminate practical-oriented solutions, tools and methods.
- Exchange knowledge through facilitated discussion, organized workshops and other activities named below.
- Stimulate and promote innovative partnerships in the EU and national AKIS.

Regarding **national level projects and initiatives**, National Coordinators will be the main contributors to this collaboration.

The added value of synergies for this target group, additionally to the described above, is:

- to co-create and integrate knowledge of EU level through facilitated discussion in national events of CFD (either demo events, workshops, annual meetings, training sessions)
- promote new partnerships and initiatives at national-level
- create national awareness on jointly tackled topics.

Policymakers: The intention of synergies with policymakers is to contribute to the “design and promotion of new policy incentives that accelerate farmers engagement in climate smart farming projects and sustainable transition”. Additionally, the project could also contribute to the “funding of further innovative climate smart farming projects to reach the objectives of the EU Climate strategy”.

The added value towards this target audience will be:

- “Get evidence of the effectiveness of climate smart practices for mitigation of GHG emission and adaptation to climate change.
- Benefit from a wide range of recommendations on networking, demos and rewarding mechanisms.”

National level policymakers will be invited to national activities whenever considered relevant to reduce the gap between farmers/advisors and policymakers and raise their awareness on the challenges and needs of the farming community.

Chapter 2

PIP Inventory

This chapter includes the Inventory of Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers identified on the 1st year of Climate Farm Demo by different actors of the consortium and external contacts. This Inventory will be updated periodically, to ensure its continuous relevance for CFD.

Inventory of Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers

One of the first tasks for this WP was developing an inventory of projects, flagship initiatives and policymakers on the EU and on national level, that was delivered as a milestone on M10 – July 2023. However, considering the importance of ensuring continuous relevance for Climate Farm Demo, as well as the importance of including upcoming PIPs, this inventory will be annually updated by using a PIP's database jointly developed with ClimateSmartAdvisors.

1.5. Mapping of relevant Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers

To ensure the PIPs in the inventory are relevant for Climate Farm Demo partners, the mapping of the identified PIPs was developed under two approaches: desk research by WP7 members and a survey targeting WPLs, TLs and NCs. WP7 developed and sent a survey to WP Leaders, Thematic Leaders, National Coordinators to identify synergies that, on a first approach, will aid them to develop their initial work and, on a second approach, will be interesting to synergy with, by creating a knowledge flow on an EU level, according to thematic, methodology, among others. Additionally, each Work Package Leader had a bilateral meeting with CONSULAI to further discuss these synergies.

1.5.1. PIPs Database

By collaborating with its sister projects, Climate Farm Demo will develop a common database, using Excel and Power BI software. Climate Farm Demo will include clear topics/thematics adapted to the Climate Farm Demo project, and each PIP coordinator will be responsible for seeking and feeding the information about each PIP to the database. The considered fields are shown on Table 1.

Table 1 - PIP's database fields

CLIMATE FARM DEMO DATABASE FIELDS		
Projects	Flagship initiatives	Policymakers
Name	Name	Name
Summary	Full name	Organization
Website	Summary	Department/Committee
Start date/End date	Website	Unit
Stage: Past (completed), On-going and Future (unestablished)	Start date and end date	Political Group
Geography level	Stage	Role
Country	Geography level	Description of role/work
Relevance for Thematic Areas	Country	Geographical level
Relevance for CFD WPs	Relevance for Thematic Leaders	Country
Agricultural Sector	Relevance for WPs	Relevance for CFD Thematic Leaders
Lead Partner	Agricultural Sector	Relevance for CFD WPs
Initiative/Programme	Attachment/Relevant documents	Biography (if available)
Funder	Contact email	Contact information
Contact email	Associated projects	Relevant background/ experience/expertise's
Attachments/Relevant documents	Funder	Attention points, Synergy opportunities
Attention points, Synergy opportunities	Attention points, Synergy opportunities	

To ensure CFD connects with relevant PIPs, over time, WP7 will assess how each PIP is relevant for each Work Package and each Thematic Area, as well as its stage and geography level. Additionally, attention points and synergy opportunities will also be identified (mainly regarding PIPs at EU level).

1.5.3. PowerBI Dashboard – PIP Report

CONSULAI is developing a report on an interactive software - Microsoft PowerBI – with three main objectives:

1. Reporting the number of identified PIPs and distribute them by the chosen categories: **Geography level, Stage and Country** were the three priority categories identified for now, but more possibilities are under development.
2. Centralizing the information of a large database into **5 dashboard pages**:
 - Overall view
 - EU Projects
 - Flagship Initiatives
 - European Policymakers
 - National Projects and Initiatives*
 - National Policymakers
3. WP7 members and other members of the consortium find relevant PIPs with whom they can develop their activities.

*The dashboard on national projects and initiatives will be made after national connections are made by CFD members – mainly National Coordinators – and if they are found to be of added value. The idea isto collect valuable national-level projects and initiatives.

The next steps will be filling out the database and have a working and updated report throughout Climate Farm Demo. A print screen of this report is shown on the next page.

Figure 3 - General report of the PIP Inventory – Power BI Dashboard (work under development)

1.6. PIP Inventory Milestone

During the first year of Climate Farm Demo, Work Package 7 developed a list of Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers both in European and national level.

1.6.1. European scale

Mapping PIPs at EU level was based on the inputs of Work Package Leaders, Thematic Leaders, Work Package 7 members and contacts made through PIPs themselves.

Overall, WP7 listed 58 Projects, 16 Initiatives and 121 policymakers. However, the list of PIPs identified will be periodically updated to include upcoming PIPs and exclude irrelevant ones.

Figure 4 - Inventory of Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers at EU level (at M12).

Due to GDPR, the lists of policymakers included in this deliverable only contain departments and roles of the policymakers (excluding their names).

EU and International Projects

The collaboration with Projects will differ regarding the stage the Projects are in:

1. **Past projects** | Synergies with Past Projects will be made indirectly and in a one-way process, through the integration of knowledge and results and through the collaboration with involved partners to collect insights and testimonies – relevant for Climate Farm Demo.
2. **On-going and future projects** | The collaboration with on-going and future projects is going to be made directly and mostly with a two way approach. Both CFD and other Projects can integrate knowledge and results throughout each Project's development, WP7 can organize joint activities and events with the other Projects. The added value is having a greater impact in the EU Community.

Regarding the relevance to thematic areas and to WPs, due to the high number of projects identified, it was not possible to conclude this analysis. However, the figures represented below show the current state of this analysis.

In terms of thematic areas, there is a balance throughout most of thematic areas of the project, However, there are a lot of projects that focus on carbon rewarding mechanisms – an urgent and relevant topic at EU and national level.

Relevance for thematic areas

Figure 5 - Inventory of Projects - Relevance to thematic areas (preliminary data).

Regarding the identified relevance for WPs, now, we've identified less projects related to MRV and Living Labs. However, as said before, this analysis is still under process, and will change in the future.

Relevance for WPs

Figure 6 - Inventory of Projects - Relevance to thematic areas (preliminary data).

The PIP Inventory includes a majority of on-going projects and a few future projects, with less focus on past projects. As explained previously, this was WP7’s goal since the collaboration with past projects limits itself to integrating project’s results and knowledge, with no active collaboration.

Stage ● Future ● On-going ● Past

Figure 7 - Inventory of Projects – Stage (preliminary data).

Flagship Initiatives

At the beginning of the project, there was no clear definition on what a flagship initiative is, so a large percentage of the identified flagship initiatives by the CFD community were not flagship initiatives, but private/public entities, associations and organizations. IFOAM and CONSULAI later established that a flagship initiative would have to have a specific aim/target group and be broader than an EU project.

At this initial stage, WP7 will only target European and International level initiatives. Due to their usual broader scope, **the aim is to target broader topics** and receive inputs or share experience and results with these initiatives. With the development of CFD, WP7 will then assess if it is relevant or not to target regional and/or national initiatives. If so, **these collaborations will be promoted through National Coordinators**.

Regarding thematic areas, the flagship initiatives identified at EU and international level include almost all thematic areas identified within the GA. Some of them were transversal to all 12 thematic areas, however 4 of them are considered to be relevant for carbon rewarding mechanisms and 4 for forage production.

Relevance for thematic areas

Figure 8 - Inventory of Initiatives - Relevance to thematic areas (preliminary data).

In terms of relevance to WPs, since the focus of initiatives tend to be broader it is natural that in a few WPs initiatives shouldn’t be as relevant – for instance in demonstration activities or MRV mechanisms,

since there aren't initiatives dedicated to those specific topics. However, topics like rewarding mechanisms, living labs and establishing national and European network, do have initiatives dedicated to them.

Relevance for WPs

Figure 9 - Inventory of Initiatives - Relevance to WPs (preliminary data).

Since initiatives have such broader topics, relevance to other WPs or thematic areas might be found.

EU Policymakers

Collaboration with European policymakers will focus on the three main European institutions: the European Commission, the European Parliament and the European Council.

The initial assessment was made through identified relevant DGs within the EU Commission, committees within the EU Parliament and attachés of the permanent representations of the countries represented in the EU Council. In total, 121 European policymakers were identified across the three institutions.

Further assessment of their relevance will be made through **reviewing policy areas and the responsibilities** of each DG, Committee and attaché and **assessing if the identified policymakers are involved in initiatives or policy making that relate to topics relevant for CFD** (carbon neutrality, sustainable farming practices, adaptation and mitigation to climate change, etc).

WP7 will also consider the **decision-making power versus the reachability of each policymaker**, as well as the dynamics of the position of policymakers in their political bodies (e.g., due to elections, or promotions), when updating the inventory/database and establishing these collaborations.

European Commission

Collaboration with the European Commission will target five directorate-generals that have been considered as relevant to the Climate Farm Demo Project:

- a) **DG AGRI** | Directorate-General for Agricultural and Rural Development
- b) **DG CLIMA** | Directorate-General for Climate Action
- c) **DG ENVI** | Directorate-General for Environment
- d) **DG ENERGY** | Directorate-General for Energy
- e) **DG RTD** | Directorate-General for Research and Innovation

European Parliament

The EU Parliament has two main committees that handle agricultural, environmental and climate change-related issues: the Committee on Agriculture and Rural Development (AGRI) and the Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI). These two committees have jurisdiction over relevant policy areas and were therefore the ones identified at this initial stage.

Due to the EU Parliament's regular elections, the Members of the European Parliament tend to change on a regular basis. Therefore, the database of PIPs will have an annual update.

WP7 listed 16 members of the AGRI Committee and 14 members of the ENVI Committee that assume different roles within the EU Parliament and are relevant to the project.

European Council

Collaboration with the EU Council aims to target national representatives through the permanent representations of the different EU countries.

Here, it is mainly attachés, counsellors and diplomats that are part of the relevant working parties, which are of great importance for Climate Farm Demo. This entails the working parties that prepare the Agriculture and Fisheries Council and the Environment Council:

- [Working Party on Agricultural Products](#)
- [Working Party on Financial Agricultural Questions \(AGRIFIN\)](#)
- [Working Party on Food and Food Systems](#)
- [Working Party on Genetic Resources and Innovation in Agriculture](#)
- [Working Party on Horizontal Agriculture Questions](#)
- [Working Party on International Food and Agricultural Questions](#)
- [Working Party on Plants and Plant Health Questions](#)
- [Working Party on the Environment](#)

1.6.2. National level

Mapping PIPs at national level was based on the inputs of National Coordinators. WP7 listed 74 projects and 87 policymakers (plus 53 from the EU Council that are national representatives in the EU).

Figure 10 - Inventory of Projects and Policymakers at national level (at M12).

The added value of establishing links with national-level PIPs and/or using existing national networks is based on the opportunity of:

- a) Disseminating CFD in other national events.
- b) Organizing joint activities and events that have the same/complementary purpose | Seize the opportunity of tackling common challenges by organizing joint events, training sessions and workshops.
- c) Connecting national and international experts and sharing knowledge and results.
- d) Contributing to the sustainability of the Project | Having a strong network established at national level is the 1st step towards the sustainability of CFD. Therefore, if this network is established with other projects and initiatives, there is a higher chance to sustain it on the long-term.

National Projects and Initiatives

Collaboration with National Projects and Initiatives will mainly have a **dissemination focus** to create national awareness about the project and the climate smart transition of agriculture. This collaboration **will mostly not fall under the responsibility of WP7, only if found relevant.**

Additionally, if found relevant for national networks, it is recommended that **National Coordinators establish collaboration with national or regional level projects and initiatives or/and with previously existing national networks.** The following scheme was used in the 2nd National Management Board Unit Meeting to show National Coordinators how they could set up their national synergies – the main attention point was the 4th: they will need to assess what is the added value of synergies. National Coordinators won't have extra work in evaluating these synergies – it will be included in the already existing evaluation method for national events (developed by BIOS).

Figure 11 - Approach to the establishment of synergies with projects and initiatives at national level (suggested by WP7 at the 2nd NMBUM).

However, if there are national-level projects and initiatives identified as relevant for WP7 organized activities, TEAGASC, IFOAM or C-KIC will establish contact.

National Policymakers

Collaboration with national policymakers will fall under the responsibility of NCs. On the previously mentioned survey, National Coordinators were asked to identify national policymakers that they found relevant for Climate Farm Demo.

When found relevant, National Coordinators are expected to invite policymakers to CFD's events such as national annual meetings, demonstration events, training and other capacity building sessions, among other examples. Additionally, policymakers will also be added to CFD's mailing list to stay updated about the project.

Chapter 3

Shaping links between PIPs and CFD

This chapter aims to describe how WP7 will shape the links between PIPs and CFD. Considering the importance of the first approach when suggesting joint activities and work, WP7 will focus on showing PIPs the added value of collaborating. Overtime, WP7 will also focus on following up the synergies made.

Shaping links

1.7. Engaging PIPs

Engaging PIPs and CFDs actors in the planning and maintaining these synergies will be one the main challenges found by this WP. The goal of organizing activities/events is not for the activity or event itself, but for the impact that that activity/event has either on the short-term, or on the long-term.

By acknowledging the main challenges the target groups may find, as well as the opportunities they have with the suggested synergies, WP7 might get actors more engaged in the planning and executing and maintaining the network.

1.7.1. Challenges found by these target groups

Time, or lack of it, is the main challenge that affects all target groups. Either due to having too many tasks and not the time to complete them, or because the establishment of these networks always involve meetings and events and can become time-consuming.

To address this issue, Work Package 7 will focus on “**Quality over quantity**“ either in the number of PIPs we establish contact with, the number and type of activities planned and the involvement of actors that lack time. Additionally, whenever possible, WP7 will seize pre-existing events to present CFD and suggest a small facilitated discussion, Q&A session, etc., if relevant (example: other project’s webinar/meeting or one of ELO’s intergroup meetings).

1.7.2. Opportunities found in synergies

The added value and opportunities found in synergies must be the main target message in cooperation meetings (this will be a priority for WP7). By finding common and complementary ground in the work developed by each PIP and CFD, these opportunities are found either by:

- Integrating new perspectives, approaches and knowledge brought by other PIPs.
- Increasing awareness of the tackled problem/task and its results and outputs.
- Reducing time spent on developing similar tasks.
- Reducing costs when arranging joint activities and events.
- Among others.

An example of how this is going to be developed is presented on section 1.8, using a Venn Diagram.

1.8. Planning the 1st Approach to a PIP

By recognizing the importance of the 1st approach when suggesting a cooperation at EU level, WP7 will focus on determining the added value of synergies and of Climate Farm Demo to each PIP through different approaches, presenting these in the first meeting.

Additionally, WP7 will consider the main challenges these groups might face – either within CFD or in general – and the benefits/opportunities they might have by building synergies with Climate Farm Demo. This 1st approach can either be made through the request of CFD consortium or of a specific PIP (demand-based approach) or by WP7 looking for opportunities in the work being developed by other PIPs.

1.8.1. In Projects and Initiatives

1. **Identify the objectives, outcomes and impacts** of each Project and Initiative, comparing them to Climate Farm Demo.
2. Searching for **similar or complementary areas of work**.
3. Searching for **opportunities for collaboration** between the involved parties: are there joint tasks to be tackled together?
4. **Compare the work being developed** by the Work Packages and other areas of the project (hubs, thematic areas, geographical areas, among others).

Venn Diagram

A cooperation material WP7 aims to do – whenever considered relevant - is a Venn Diagram of both PIPs, since it clearly shows the added value and complementarity between projects/initiatives.

Figure 12 - Venn Diagram (ClieNFarms' example)

Each PIP's progress and timing will be considered and compared to CFD, given that Projects and Initiatives that already have results and outputs tend to have a different added value than the ones that are on its beginning.

1.8.2. In Policymakers

1. **Gaining insight into the subjects and regulations** that the relevant policymaker is working on.

This will vary across European Institutions. For MEPs, for instance, understanding their involvement in certain committees and their specific responsibilities within those would prove valuable.

2. Subsequently, it is important to **introduce Climate Farm Demo**, its concrete objectives, and the anticipated results.

Initially, as project outcomes are yet to be realized, this explanation will be confined to the content stipulated in the grant agreement and the insights gained during consortium meetings. In this phase, maintaining ongoing communication with other work packages becomes crucial, enabling us to remain abreast of their progress and tailor our communication accordingly.

3. As a third step, it is crucial to identify synergies by **understanding the policymakers' needs**.

Depending on policies being developed, scientific insights gained from field-level observations or comprehensive information in the areas addressed by Climate Farm Demo could be highly relevant. Moreover, if required, we can connect them with partners or farmers from CFD. While these scenarios are speculative, the exact needs can only be determined through dialogue.

4. **Maintain communication.**

In initial interactions, progressing to step 4 might not always be feasible, as certain policymakers may have commitments elsewhere that prevent them from engaging extensively with this Horizon project. However, with those where a strong synergy is apparent, it's crucial to keep the connection alive and develop it even further. This involves staying in touch, enrolling them for newsletters, providing consistent updates, and inviting them to relevant events.

Venn Diagram

Similarly to Projects and Initiatives, Venn Diagrams serve as a common tool to visually represent the potential synergies and the degree of overlap between the project and the policymaker.

Figure 13 - Venn Diagram (Policymaker example)

1.9. Knowledge Exchange Thematics

The topics of the knowledge exchange within WP7 activities will focus under 4 thematics:

Climate Smart Farming | Being the core of Climate Farm Demo Project, this topic will be a priority for WP7 related activities since it regards all Work Packages. Despite being a large-scale project with various partners, Climate Farm Demo will benefit from knowledge and research from other PIPs regarding this topic.

- Regarding WPs: All WPs.

On-farm Demonstration | Considering that behaviour change in farmers will be a challenge, on farm demonstration was chosen as an efficient method to facilitate climate smart farming transition. However, by collaborating and exchanging knowledge with other PIPs, CFD's demo events will be enhanced to better target farmers. This topic regards WP1, WP2 and WP3.

- Regarding WPs: WP1, WP2 and WP3

Innovation uptake in general | Similarly to the previous topic, innovation uptake can also be a challenge among farmers, especially due to the existing gap between theory and practice in upcoming technologies and innovations. There is a large effort among EU partners and organizations that participate in R&D Projects to reduce this gap by facilitating farmers' transition to a more sustainable and innovative agriculture.

- Regarding WPs: WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP6

AKIS's Capacity Building – The required transition of the agricultural sector, that centers on the Adaptation and Mitigation of Climate Change – will not only require change in farmers and at farm scale, but it will also require change among every peer in the sector (and should therefore involve capacity building within the AKIS).

- Regarding WPs: WP1, WP6, WP7

Chapter 4

Participation and organization of coordinated events and producing policy briefs.

This chapter introduces the first plan and calendar of the activities and events organized by CFD or in which CFD participates in. Moreover, it covers the type of activities and thematics planned to be developed as well as the possible outputs of the WP.

Knowledge Exchange generated through PIP activities

WP7's activities will be built based on the needs of Climate Farm Demo, throughout the seven years. In the beginning of the project, WPLs and TLs will give input on the selection of PIPs with which CFD might develop the synergies, and afterwards, through desk work and brief meetings, CONSULAI will identify possible topics and time for synergy activities.

To guarantee a specific number of events per year, the chosen PIPs will only be identified in each year's DAP. In this document, each year's activity will be addressed, with as much detail as possible (regarding thematics, target groups involved, etc).

1.9.1. Types of knowledge exchange activities planned in T7.3

The activities planned for Task 7.3 will differ based on the regarding PIP/target audience, the expected outcome and the methodology planned.

Activities can either be online or face-to-face, and will be sub-divided into four types:

1. **Online meetings and workshops** | Knowledge exchange online meetings on topics identified by Climate Farm Demo partners. These activities can either be organized and prepared by WP7 or the participation of PIPs/CFD actors is facilitated by WP7 (example: there is a webinar on Water Management organized by ClieNFarms and WP7's facilitates the participation of the thematic leader responsible).
2. **Participation in other PIPs events/Conferences/Other externally organized events** | Disseminate Climate Farm Demo's results and outputs to other PIPs and obtain information on what is being developed to create cooperation.
3. **Invitation to CFDs events (lectures, workshops, webinars, ...)** | Invite partners from other PIPs to contribute to and learn from Climate Farm Demo (by a workshop, a presentation, a facilitated discussion, etc).
4. **EU-level workshops** | 3 Workshops at EU-level with a chosen thematic. These events will be held the latest on Year 3 (2024-2025), Year 4 (2025-2026) and Year 6 (2027-2028).

The following table shows the considered values for planning, organizing and participating, and disseminating and evaluating each type of activity/event.

Table 2 - Description of each type of activity to be planned by WP7 - Estimate of PMs spent on planning, executing and evaluating.

Expected outcome	Type of collaboration	Description	PIP targeted	Budget necessary	PMs necessary (for organization)			
					Planning	Executing	Evaluating	Total
Participation in other PIPs meetings/conferences/other externally organized events Knowledge sharing sessions	External (other PIPs events)	Participation in other projects and flagship initiatives meetings.	Projects Flagship initiatives	Travel budget or none (online meetings).	0.2 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.4 PMs
Invitation to CFDs events (lectures, workshops, webinars, ...) Knowledge sharing sessions	Internal (CFD events)	Invitation for PIPs to participate in CFD 's events (demonstration, KE activities, workshops, conferences).	Projects Flagship initiatives	Travel budget or none (online).	0.1 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.3PMs
Organized online workshop Knowledge sharing sessions with WPL or TLs	Mixed	Workshops between WP Leaders and/or Thematic Leaders and other actors – Based on the needs of both parties.	WPL, TLs, NCs, Projects, Flagship Initiatives.	None (online).	0.2 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.2 PMs	0.5 PMs
Participation in national events Demonstration events/National KE meetings	Internal with external actors.	Facilitate the participation of policymakers in national KE meetings/ demonstration.	Policymakers, National or regional projects, Flagship Initiatives. (TL?)	-	0 PMs	0 PMs	0.1PM	0.1 PMs
Organized online Workshop - Knowledge sharing sessions by 4 Clusters	Mixed	Organized workshops with policy makers (online).	Policymakers and NCs	None (online).	0.2 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.2 PMs	0.5 PMs
Participation in meetings/events Data and results sharing sessions	External	Data and results sharing sessions The goal will be to disseminate the projects data and results in meetings/events.	All (including national projects)	Travel budget or none (online meetings).	0.2 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.1 PMs	0.4 PMs
EU-level policy workshop Workshop organized for 15 to 20 people)	External	Organized workshops with policy makers (face-to-face).	Policymakers	Travel Budget and other types of costs	0.4 PMs	0.3 PMs	0.3 PMs	1 PMs

Considering that WP7 aims to do high impact activities, it has estimated that the planning, executing and evaluating of the events will have to be done thoroughly:

1. Planning the events is considered to take up on average 0.2PMs since most of the events involve two people planning and include the linkage to PIPs, assessing complementarities on the developed work and jointly finding common ground.
2. Executing will take on average 0.1 PMs as a minimum value, since it will most likely involve two or three people, travel time and time to execute the event (pre and post time included),
3. Evaluating will take on average 0.1 or 0.2 PMs since it will involve the monitoring process (data collection and analysis and development of reports) characterized in Chapter 5.

In the case that less PMs are used, WP7 will adjust the number and types of activities planned for the project. For instance, presenting CFD on an already planned webinar will involve less PMs in executing and evaluating. Therefore, these PMs can be adjusted for future use.

1.9.2. Calendar

According to the available budget, person months and travels, as well as the numbers presented in Table 2, WP7 estimated the annual plan for activities and events within this WP. However, the plan for activities is subject to change over the years, and will therefore be updated accordingly.

Table 3 - 7-year plan of activities and events for WP7

Types of events	Y2 2023 – 2024	Y3 2024 - 2025	Y4 2025 - 2026	Y5 2026 - 2027	Y6 2027 - 2028	Y7 2028 - 2029
Online meetings and workshops	1	2	3	3	3	3
Participation in events/meetings	1	3	4	4	4	4
Invitation to CFDs events/meetings	1	2	3	3	3	3
Workshops planned for T7.3	0	1	1	0	1	0
Annual meetings with sister projects	0	>1	>1	>1	>1	>1
Conferences with sister projects	0	0	0	1	0	1
Total	3	10	13	13	13	13

1.10. Joint CDE activities

To increase the visibility of the Project, BIOS has established different approaches related to joint communication and dissemination activities, based on an established “core group” of projects – considered to be the most relevant to collaborate directly in CDE activities:

- a) Periodical CDE meetings
- b) Cross-posting with some of the PIPs we synergy with | Disseminate relevant content (activities, surveys and events) of other PIPs on CFD’s social media ad newsletters.

Regarding initiatives and policymakers, if possible, WP7 will establish a joint communication strategy and share their relevant content on CFD’s social media.

1.11. Knowledge repository

WP7 will create a knowledge repository with the outputs of the meetings, events and activities either organized by WP7, or that may be relevant for cooperation at national and EU level (for example, the impact of policymakers' participation at demoevents).

WP7 aims to have reports of joint events and workshops focused on specific thematic that WP7 and the collaborative PIPs consider to be relevant.

1.12. Policy Briefs

One of the outputs of Work Package will be the production of policy briefs that will cover relevant thematic for Climate Smart Farming. The aim of the policy briefs is to **strategically engage national or EU-level legislation**. This is achieved by offering an analysis of the current legislative landscape and suggesting enhancements based on insights derived from Climate Farm Demo. Alternatively, the briefs can originate from Climate Farm Demo findings, leading to the formulation of recommendations for new legislation.

This approach facilitates bridging the perspectives of the agricultural community with both current and forthcoming policies and may therefore allow for improved policy evaluation and design on climate smart farming. ELO is responsible for the production of five policy briefs.

1.12.1. Addressed thematic

Five policy briefs will be produced throughout the project covering five broad thematic that are closely linked with the project's objectives: **networking, demos, living labs, rewarding mechanisms and cooperation**.

These thematic will be considered the broad topic of each policy brief, however WP7 will later specify the addressed topics according to relevant subjects. Given the extensive duration of the project, it's not feasible to predetermine the specific thematic areas, considering the unpredictability of upcoming legislation. Currently, issues such as the nature restoration law, soil monitoring, CAP reforms, and carbon removal certifications are highly relevant and at the top of the European agenda. Nevertheless, **the focus might shift to different subjects in the following years**.

The objective is to always communicate about important topics that people care about and march what's relevant at the time. The policy briefs are expected to **contribute to support and strengthen the implementation of the CAP and EU climate Policy**.

1.12.2. Activities organized to give input for policy briefs

WP7 will organize a few events with European policymakers in which the focus will be discussing policy and can therefore bring input for policy briefs.

Moreover, all activities organized within this WP – due to its connection to a wide EU and national level network – and outside of it, might provide input for policy briefs because of the valuable insights gained during the events from different stakeholders. The results and outputs of the project bring new knowledge and change the view on the needs of the agricultural systems.

On the other hand, WP7 will promote the participation of national policymakers on CFD's national events that are already planned under the project. The idea will be for National Coordinators to invite national policymakers for demo events, national knowledge exchange activities, among others, and involve them in CFD.

Chapter 5

Collaboration with sister projects on Climate Smart Agriculture

Collaboration with Climate Smart Advisors and possibly the third sister project of this Climate Smart Trilogy will be key. It's a priority for all the projects to stay aligned when tackling the transition to climate smart farming and, therefore, regular meetings and events are planned to ensure this happens.

Develop a close collaboration with Climate Smart Farming related Projects

Climate Farm Demo and Climate Smart Advisors both focus on the **urgent transition to a climate smart agriculture**. While Climate Farm Demo will focus on farmers on the primary actors of change to climate-smart farming, ClimateSmartAdvisors was created on the idea that tackling large-scale challenges such as climate change need to involve the whole farming community – focusing, therefore, on the advisory community.

There was a third project to implemented under the topic to be published in **Cluster 6 work programme 2023/2024 - “Linking Experimental Farms”** that was considered relevant for CFD. However, since the project wasn’t approved, we will consider this project as a possible connection for Climate Farm Demo, if approved on the work programme 2024/2025, and therefore beginning on the fourth year of CFD.

1.13. Introducing ClimateSmartAdvisors

ClimateSmartAdvisors is a pan-European multi-actor network covering 27 countries. Its aim is to boost the EU agricultural advisory community, leading to an acceleration of the adoption of climate smart (CS) farming practices by the wider farming community within and across EU AKISs. To reach this objective, Climate Smart Advisors focuses on the crucial role of advisors in the development and dissemination of CS innovations and practices. The project will organize activities focusing on strengthening the advisors’ capacity in providing CS advice and boosting the advisors’ role in the transition towards CS farming through their involvement in innovation projects, CS-AKIS, and EU projects and initiatives. Several complementary activities are developed to strengthen the CS advisory capacity of the EU advisory community:

1. an EU-wide network of 260 advisory Communities of Practice (CoP) to support the development of 1500 advisors will form the core of CS knowledge exchange.
2. 140 advisors will receive expert training on selected topics, relevant for their context and for facilitating a CoP.
3. CoPs will internationally exchange knowledge on 12 thematic areas.
4. a knowledge repository will provide advisors with CS tools, practices and approaches developed in the Climate Farm Demo project and further expanded in ClimateSmartAdvisors,

5. monitoring, evaluation and learning activities will capitalize lessons learned in and outside the project.

Activities to boost the advisors’ role in the CS transition include:

- Connecting to local and EU (multi-actor innovation) projects, initiatives, AKIS actors, and policy makers to clarify and address joint needs, challenges and lessons learned,
- Set-up of Co-Design Innovation Experiments to learn on how to strengthen the advisors’ role in innovation processes.

Finally, to accelerate the wide spread of results, an ambitious dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy will be deployed at EU and national levels.”

1.14. Knowledge Exchange generated in Synergies with Sister Projects

The collaboration with sister projects will rely on the CFD’s coordinator (IDELE), as well as CONSULAI as leader of the Work Package 7 (from CFD’s side). This collaboration will build **strong links between the projects that aim to facilitate the transition to Climate Smart Farming** with different focus areas: commercial farms, advisory services and experimental farms.

This collaboration will focus on how to cooperate, how to tackle joint tasks and how to complement the work being developed in the projects.

1.14.1. Calendar

Table 4 - Calendar for WP7’s activities regarding sister projects.

	Y2 2023 – 2024	Y3 2024 - 2025	Y4 2025 - 2026	Y5 2026 - 2027	Y6 2027 - 2028	Y7 2027 - 2028	Y8 2028 – 2029
Annual Meetings with Climate Smart Advisors	-	> 1	> 1	> 1	> 1	> 1	> 1
Joint Conferences	-	-	-	-	1	-	1

1.14.1.1 2023 – 2024 | Plan for cooperation – Part I

The activities have started on May 2023, on the Kick-off Meeting of the Climate Smart Advisors Project, where CFD was introduced to the CSA consortium. Additionally, WP7 surveyed the CSA consortium through Mentimeter on “How can CFD and CSA cooperate?”.

Initially the focus will be on the establishing each Project network and work before any collaboration activities are made. Therefore, at this stage, CSA is planning and starting to deliver their tasks – and no “active” collaboration is previewed.

WP7 and coordination from both CFD and CSA will schedule meetings to start planning collaboration and assess where both projects can act jointly on the baseline of collaboration – either in national networks, thematic networks, etc.

1.14.1.2 2024 – 2030 | Plan for cooperation – Part II

The actual organization of joint events and activities will be developed from 2024 – 2025 onwards. To plan annual synergies, coordination and WP7 members will meet on a regular basis. Additionally, CFD and CSA will plan joint conferences, further described below.

1.14.2. Types of activities and events

1.14.2.1 Annual meetings with sister projects

WP7 and the coordination team from both projects will meet regularly to make sure these projects stay aligned and cooperate in joint tasks as much as possible. These named annual meetings do not refer to joint general assemblies of the projects, but to regular meetings between projects coordinators, WP7 and other relevant WPs.

1.14.2.2 Joint conferences

The joint conferences to be planned are organized with dedicated workshops specially intended to establish working connections and synergies among the two projects, and if relevant, with other EU Projects focuses on farm demonstration and on climate smart transition (such as IPM Works).

Furthermore, climate smart practices and results will be shared systematically, along with experiences and other relevant data about the Climate Farm Demo Project, other EU Projects and the climate transition of agriculture.

These events are planned to be held on Year 5 (2025-2026) and Year 7 (2028-2029).

Chapter 6

Monitoring PIP Activities

Linking CFD to other PIPs is only successful if it enhances collaboration when tackling joint challenges - in this case, climate change and the urgent need of transitioning to a more resilient farming. However, measuring cooperation will be a challenge. This chapter describes the monitoring and tracking plan to be established by WP7.

Monitoring PIP Activities

1.15. Monitoring

Keeping track of the activities and events organized between Climate Farm Demo and other PIPs is the first step towards monitoring the success of the WP. Therefore, there will be a database of activities and events that will keep track of what is happening towards this WP.

CONSULAI will monitor the database ensuring that PIP Coordinators and Sister Project Coordinator are up to date in their reporting responsibility.

Each activity will be monitored during its planning, execution and afterwards, using template reports adapted to each type of activity. There will be two categories for monitoring: in terms of the event set-up, objectives, methodology used (...), and in terms of content/knowledge exchanged.

The base structure will include 2 perspectives - **the participants and the organization team** - as well as two different approaches **before the event has taken place** and **afterwards**.

Figure 14 - Structure of surveys made to evaluate activities.

This will allow WP7 to compare what was planned and expected versus what happened – the evaluation of this comparison will feed the annual assessment reports allowing the continuous improvement strategy suggested by the WP.

1.15.1. Monitoring through the planning phase

Both WP7 Partners and organization actors will be asked to give input for monitoring either in the planning and execution phase, by developing an action plan.

Additionally, when signing up to an event, participants will be asked about their expectations and motivations to participate in the event.

1.15.2. Monitoring through the evaluation phase

Participants will be asked to evaluate the event afterwards. The input that participants will give during the event – in facilitated discussions, mentimeter and other surveys – will also be used to evaluate the impact of the event.

WP7 members and other organizing team members will evaluate the events and activities by:

- a) Comparing participants survey pre and post event.
- b) Have a note keeper during the event.
- c) Filling the WP7 evaluation report.

1.16. Keeping track

WP7 will keep track of the activities and meetings happening at WP-level and externally by using a database file in excel. The following table shows the fields used in the tracking database, the type of data and the Kick off Meeting of Climate Smart Advisors as an example.

The goal of this table is for the core information of each activity/event to be stored in a single document and for the reports to each activity have links within this same database.

Table 4 - Tracking database of WP7 activities (database fields, type of data and example)

Fields	Type of data	Example
From (Date)	dd/mm/yyyy	30/05/2023
To (Date)	dd/mm/yyyy	01/06/2023
Type of event	Annual Meeting (Project/National level), Conference, Workshop, Webinar, Cross-PIP Meeting, n/a	Annual Meeting (Project-level)
Name of event	(name)	Kick-off Meeting Climate Smart Advisors
Date of the activity	dd/mm/yyyy	30/05/2023
Type of activity	Conference, Workshop, demo event, webinar, lecture/presentation, group discussion, training session, cross-PIP meeting	Lecture/Presentation
Title of the meeting/session/event		Introducing Climate Farm Demo
PIPs in the organization (Group)	Projects, Initiatives, Policymakers	Projects
PIPs in the organization	Projects' name(s)	Climate Smart Advisors
PIPs in the organization	Initiatives' name(s)	n/a
PIPs in the organization	Policymakers' name(s)	n/a
Target PIPs	Projects, Initiatives and/or Policymakers	Projects
Target Groups (AKIS)	Farmers, advisors, researchers, industry, other stakeholders, n/a	n/a
Geographic Scope	National, European, International	European
Predicted Audience (number)	(number)	90

Collaboration	Joint activity/event, External conference, Activity/event of CFD with external PIP, Activity/event of external PIP with CFD	Activity/Event of external PIP with CFD
WP7 Responsible	WP partners (dropdown list)	CONSULAI, IDELE
Action Plan (progress)	YES/ IN PROGRESS/ NO	NO
Action Plan (link)	(link)	(link)
Execution Report (progress)	YES/ IN PROGRESS/ NO	NO
Execution Plan (link)	(link)	(link)
Proof (relevant documents)	Attached document, photo (emails, presentations, photos of the events, leaflets, etc)	(Documents, photos, other files)

To ensure that most synergies happening in CFD – whether they’re organized by WP7 members or not – are reported to this WP, CONSULAI will regularly remind CFD actors to inform them about past, on-going or future collaborations in the Executive Committee Meetings for WP Leaders and Task Leaders, NMBU Meetings for NCs and Thematic Leaders Meetings for TLs.

1.17. Reporting | Dynamic Assessment Plans and Assessment Reports

Annually, in September (M12 and onwards), IFOAM will produce a dynamic action plan describing the general preview of the work to be developed by WP7 on the following year. To evaluate the work developed by WP7 in that year, in August (M23 and onwards), BIOS will develop an annual assessment report. The base calendar of the documents’ delivery is found on Table 5.

Table 5 - Seven-year calendar on the delivery of action plans and assessment reports on WP7's activities.

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7
Dynamic Action Plan Delivery	M12	M24	M36	M48	M60	M72	
Assessment Report Delivery		M23	M35	M47	M59	M71	M83

Chapter 7

Results, Outcomes and Impacts

The collaboration and cooperation at EU and national level – which is the main goal of this WP – will be assessed through the results, outcomes, and impacts that regard WP7 and these connections. This chapter characterizes the methodology for measuring outcomes and impacts of the synergies made.

Results, outcomes and impacts

The cooperation driven by WP7 between CFD and other PIPs is only considered successful if it brings inputs, knowledge exchange, expertise sharing and peer-to-peer discussions that are found useful for two aims: **for the development of CFD (on the short term)** or to **drive the transition to a more climate resilient farming sector (on the long term)**. The workflow for WP7's progress is described in Figure 15.

The measurement of this success in this WP will be its main challenge. WP7 will focus on establishing metrics and KPIs to keep track of the development of synergies, assessing the added value on both perspectives (CFD and PIP involved).

Figure 15 - Workflow on WP7

1.18. Differences between results, outcomes and impact

The results will be measured and evaluated during the Project's development through the assessment of the success of the different activities and events in which WP7 is involved, or that WP7 organizes. It will mainly evaluate the **links and collaboration that are happening at EU and national level**, and **general outputs of these synergies** such as common communication and dissemination materials, joint activities reports that may target a specific group in the farming community, etc.

Synergies' outcomes and impacts will be assessed towards the end of the project and after it has ended, since the focus will be on the **potential influence these collaborations may have towards the climate smart transition of agriculture**. WP7 will focus on assessing if these collaborations have led to identifiable (objective) changes such as:

- a) contributed to new projects or initiatives – either at national or at European level
- b) had influence in the design of new policies through joint policy briefs and recommendations.
- c) Contributed to the development of strong national and European networks, that will continue to exist after the project has ended.
- d) Reduce redundant R&D projects by optimising the use of allocated resources.

1.19. Metrics and Key Performance Indicators

Work Package 7 will establish relevant metrics and KPIs to assess the performance of the WP. To ensure synergies were evaluated with a comprehensible and balanced view, metrics and KPIs will either be quantitative – based on numbers, data and statistics – and qualitative – based on opinions, feedback and observations that are represented by scale answers (“On a scale from 1 to 10, how would you rate the participants engagement in this session?”).

Additionally, KPIs will be updated whenever considered relevant by WP members, while metrics will be measured annually, contributing to the evaluation of WP7's progress.

Both KPIs and metrics are focused on 3 main aims:

1. **Measuring actual contact with PIPs** | How many projects, initiatives and policymakers are contacted, how many cross-PIP meetings WP7 had (either for 1st contact or for planning and evaluating joint activities and follow up).
2. **Tracking activities/events** | Tracking number and type of activities within the WP, Assess PIPs engagement, etc.
3. **Assessing the outcomes and impacts of collaboration** | Number and type of outputs and follow-up meetings, EU wide awareness, new-coming projects or initiatives, policy influence rating, sustainability of the cooperation/synergy (follow-up activities/meetings/outputs).

1.19.1. Quantitative assessment

WP7 will develop a list of relevant indicators that can be measured throughout the events and activities planned that will be regarded as metrics and KPIs for this WP.

Whenever possible, KPIs and metrics will follow the SMART parameters:

- **Specific** | What exactly do you want to achieve?
- **Measurable** | How will you identify that you have achieved your goal?
- **Attainable** | Is your goal achievable?
- **Relevant** | Is this relevant/Does this align with where the WP wants to be?
- **Time-Bound** | When will this goal be delivered? What are the key milestones?

1.19.1.1 KPIs | Deliverable and Milestones of WP7 and Planned activities

Considering KPIs related to cooperation and collaboration to be difficult to estimate, WP7 focused on establishing metrics, using less KPIs. The KPIs established were the planned activities for WP7, and the deliverables and milestones of the WP, presented in Table 6 and Table 7.

Work Package 7 has 2 deliverables and 15 milestones designed to assess its progress throughout the work beyond CFD's network.

Table 6 - Deliverables and Milestones for WP7

Deliverable/Milestone name	KPI	Month
PIP Inventory (MS)	1	M10 (afterwards it will be annually updated)
Strategic Plan for the PIPs (D)	1	M12
PIP Strategic Plan prepared and validated by partners (MS)	1	M18
Established PIP links (MS)	1	M24
Dynamic Action Plans (MS)	6	M12, M24, M36, M48, M60, M72
Assessment Reports (MS)	6	M23, M35, M47, M59, M71, M83
Sustainability Plan for the Network (D)	1	M82

Table 7 - KPIs for WP7 (planned activities and events)

Types of events	Y2 2023 – 2024	Y3 2024 - 2025	Y4 2025 - 2026	Y5 2026 - 2027	Y6 2027 - 2028	Y7 2028 - 2029
Online meetings and workshops	1	2	3	3	3	3
Participation in events/meetings	1	3	4	4	4	4
Invitation to CFDs events/meetings	1	2	3	3	3	3
Workshops planned for T7.3	0	1	1	0	1	0
Conferences with sister projects	0	0	0	1	0	1
Annual Meetings with Climate Smart Advisors + Third Sister Project	0	>1	>1	>1	>1	>1
Total	3	10	13	13	13	13

1.19.1.3 Metrics on WP7's progress

Based on the action plan and evaluation reports made by WP7 members, an annual and global assessment of the activities will be made to keep track of the WP. A description of each metric is described in Table 8, where the two types of indicators are categorized by time-frame: global, annual and by activity.

Table 8 - Metrics on WP7's progress (global assessment).

Metrics	Description	Measurement	Timing	
			Global	Annual
Number of cross-PIP meetings	Number of meetings established between CFD and PIPs (1st approach, planning and reporting events, follow-up meetings, etc)	Tracking database	X	
Number of Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers contacted	Number of first contacts to PIPs in order to establish synergies (emails, meetings, among others)	DAPs, Assessment Reports WP7 and ExCom Meetings Other sources	X	X
Number and type of activities organized	(Joint, by CFD, by PIP – CFD is invited) & (workshop, webinar, conference, meeting, fair, lecture, etc)	DAPs, Assessment Reports Tracking database	X	X
Number of collaborative outputs	Number of joint reports, evaluations and other outputs from Joint Sessions/Workshops.	Tracking database	X	X
EU wide awareness (number of people reached on all social media and website/number of people reached on CFDs media and website)	Evaluate the degree to which cooperative efforts have increased visibility and recognition across different EU regions and stakeholders (mainly by joining CDE channels and consortium).	Survey	X	X
New projects, initiatives or programmes created due to collaboration	Survey in 4 years designed either for the national and european level	Survey/Follow up meeting	X	

1.19.1.4 Metrics on activities and target groups

Similarly to before, a description of each metric is described in Table 9.

Table 9 - Metrics on WP7's progress (by activities and target groups).

Metric	Description	Time-frame		
		Global	Annual	By activity
Type of activities organized	Are the activities balanced between interactive sessions (workshops and facilitated discussion), lecture type sessions (webinars and presentations) and CDE materials (joint press releases and others)?	X	X	X
Target audience (number and group)	How many people participated in WP7 activities?	X	X	X
Group and individual engagement	How do participants evaluate their engagement and the group's engagement on each activity?	X	X	X
Targeted WPs/Thematic Areas by activity	Assess the balance between WPs and Thematic Areas targetet – Is WP7 focusing on specific groups or is it balanced out? If we do focus on a specific group, it should have a reason.	X	X	X

Cooperation and Intervention	Did participants feel like they had opportunity to exchange knowledge and intervene?	X	X	X
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1.19.2. Qualitative assessment

Qualitative assessment will focus on **opinions, feedback and observations**, either made in the activities organized/attended, or on post-event survey or follow-up meetings.

A few examples of the questions used in this type of assessment are:

- a) “Were there any aspects of the [meeting] that were particularly successful?”
- b) “Conversely, were there any areas that could have been improved?”
- c) “Was the content up to date and relevant?”
- d) “Was the content/experiences shared/facilitated discussion relevant for the work you currently need to develop?”
- e) “Do you consider future cooperation to be of added value?”

This type of questions can bring a comprehensible input to the assessment of the WP, **enabling a holistic approach to the evaluation of its progress** – that doesn’t rely solely on data and statistics.

Chapter 8

Risk analysis for Work Package 7

Considering that a Work Package focused on collaboration has the main risk of not having collaborative participants and therefore cannot succeed in this collaboration, WP7 has identified the main risks within their WP, identifying possible mitigation measures.

Risk analysis

Having in mind that the planning and collaboration between the identified actors has its risks, WP7 developed a risk analysis to identify prevention or mitigation measures. This analysis follows a risk flow that starts on the regarded task and objective, the possible risk and finally the mitigation measure – these categories are only considered on specific risk tables, when found relevant.

Establishing the PIPs network

Table 10 - Risk analysis for WP7 (I) - Establishing the PIPs Network.

	Task	Objective/Goal	Risk/Barrier	Mitigation measure
Establishing the PIP network	PIP Inventory	Choosing PIPs regarding the needs and tasks of NCs, CFAs and PDFs.	PIPs not suited to CFDs needs. Miss important PIPs	Survey to CFDs actors to identify main needs/challenges and barriers to their work, as well as examples of relevant PIPs.
	PIP Database	Functional and updated database (at least) throughout the project's life	After delivering the PIP inventory, the database stops being used/developed.	Excel Database and Power BI dashboards will be used to ensure interactivity within the WP7 partners. This database will be the only storage for PIP information (contact, relevance for CFD, etc.) and it will be updated every year to ensure its continuous use. DAP and Assessment report: the updated synergies will be presented in each years DAP/AS and on the database.
	Establishing 1st contact	Suggestion of cooperating and building synergies between PIPs and CFDs actors.	Uninterested and uncooperative PIPs	Clearly demonstrate the added value of the project on the 1st approach. Present benefits from these synergies to each actor. Explain the strategy for WP7 activities.

Target Groups of WP7

Table 11 - Risk analysis for WP7 (II) - Target Groups.

Risk/Challenge/Barrier	Target Group(s)	Mitigation measure
Lack of time to dedicate to these synergies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Projects • Flagship Initiatives • EU Policymakers • National Policymakers • WP Leaders • National Coordinators • Thematic Leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Quality over quantity” Focus is not on having lots of events with numerous PIPs involved but to plan synergies that focus on successful knowledge exchange. • Regarding EU policymakers, WP7 will mainly focus on organizing 3 EU level workshops that will target them specifically.
Lack of alignment between objectives, methodologies and priorities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Projects • Flagship Initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Quality over quantity” Focus on Projects and Initiatives with common and complementary objectives/tasks to ensure these synergies have an actual impact. • Assess the complementarities and common tasks/objectives between the PIPs. • Desk work on comparing WPs and common partners
<p>Changing of roles in the EU institutions within the project's timeline: Upcoming elections are scheduled for June 2024 and occur every 5 years: →Significant transformation in the composition of various institutions (particularly in the parliament), →New commissioners will assume their roles àThe EU Council follows a six-month rotating presidency, with Spain currently holding it until January (followed by Belgium's takeover). Each country brings their own priorities à Adding a new layer of potential policy changes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annually update the database to ensure the policymakers added are active within the 3 institutions. Whenever there are elections or changing, update the database.
Changing of CAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Policymakers • National Policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closely follow the CAP revision to adapt the Project activities and objectives to the potential policy changes.
Lack of awareness and understanding of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Projects • Flagship Initiatives • EU Policymakers • National Policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The 1st approach must show the added value of CFD towards climate smart transition at an European scale and national scale.
Different countries (with different AKIS, context, agricultural sectors, etc) need different approaches to farmers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include National Coordinators when collaborating with national policymakers.
Amount of work to be done in the project may not encourage them to be active and engaged in synergy activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP Leaders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve them in planning the synergies for each year – Assess their needs and challenges in CFD and see if collaboration with PIPs could be of use. • WP7 has a good number of PMs to support and drive forward the other WPs.

Planning and developing activities and events

Table 12 - Risk Analysis for WP7 (III) - Organizing activities and events.

	Risk/Barrier	Mitigation measure
Planning and developing synergy activities	Events/activities not suited to the target audience or to the content. Irrelevant content → Uninterested actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey to CFDs actors to identify which type of initiatives/activities would work best for their challenges. • Involving PIPs and CFDs actors in planning and organizing activities.
	Uncooperative EU project and flagship initiative partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of a facilitator in the events/activities that require discussion and knowledge exchange. • Continuous improvement strategy: report/feedback from past activities are taken into consideration when planning future activities. • Involving PIPs and CFDs actors in planning and organizing activities.
	Uncooperative European and national policymakers.	
	Uncooperative WPL, Thematic Leaders, National Coordinators.	
	Diversity of topics/ thematics/ sectors addressed could make the synergy topics too broad.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize technical topics that may be upscaled to become relevant to all AKIS actors.

Short-term outcome and long-term impact

Table 13 - Risk analysis for WP7 (IV) – Short term outcomes and long-term Impact.

	Task	Objective/Goal	Risk/Barrier	Mitigation measure
RESULTS AND OUTPUTS	Short term impact (2022 - 2029)	Evaluate short-term impact .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of SMART metrics to measure and monitor short-term impact (=outcomes) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative focus of the survey post-event - Feedback from participants and organizers of the events after the event and after some time has passed. Quantitative focus of the survey post-event (number of participants, types of target groups, number and type of activities, among other indicators).
		Give inputs for CFD's main challenges through topics addressed in these meetings.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zero follow-up contact or knowledge exchange between partners. Follow-up contact only happens with WP7 collaboration (collaboration depends on WP7). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share contact list within the events organized (including their relevant role in the topic)
OUTCOME AND IMPACT	Long term impact (2029 - further on)	Evaluate long-term impact .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (challenge) Lack of qualitative indicators to measure and monitor long-term impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collective feedback from the synergies and links developed with each PIP.
		Create a lasting national cooperation and knowledge exchange network .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The national networks created for CFD end short after the Project ends. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the beginning of the Project, advise NCs to contact existing networks, initiatives and projects, and create a national CFD network supported on this already existing national network. Involve national policymakers and other AKIS actors in CFD's national events.
		Create a European cooperation and knowledge exchange network .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The materials, results and other outputs produced in CFD are not considered for further usage, nor updated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP8 will create a training toolbox with materials and sessions available in e-learning.

Chapter 9

Annexes

List of EU Projects identified:

Annex 1 - List of Projects at european and international level.

Name	Summary/Attention points	Website	Stage	Geography Level
NEFERTITI	NEFERTITI focuses on creating added value from the exchange of knowledge, actors, farmers and technical content over the networks in order to boost innovation uptake, to improve peer to peer learning and network connectivity between farms actors across Europe, thus contributing to a more competitive, sustainable and climate-smart agriculture.	https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/	Past	European
ClieNFarms	ClieNFarms is based on 20 demonstration case-studies (I3S) where systemic innovative solutions will be tested and evaluated using up-to-date modelling approaches and multicriteria assessment tools. These case-studies will pave the diversity of the production systems (crops, cattle, dairy, special crop productions, etc) and the diversity of geographical situations (from East to West and North to South of Europe, plus one in New-Zealand).	https://cliefarms.eu/	On-going	European
IPM Works	The objective of IPMWORKS is to promote the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies, based on a EU-wide network of farmers, who will both progress further in the adoption of IPM – through peer-to-peer learning and joint efforts – and demonstrate to other farmers that holistic IPM “works”; i.e. allows a low reliance on pesticides with better pest control, reduced costs and enhanced profitability.	https://ipmworks.net/	On-going	European
Climate Smart Advisors	ClimateSmartAdvisors aims is to boost the EU agricultural advisory community, leading to an acceleration of the adoption of climate smart (CS) farming practices by the wider farming community within and across EU AKISs. To reach this objective, ClimateSmartAdvisors focuses on the crucial role of advisors in the development and dissemination of CS innovations and practices.	-	On-going	European
Linking Research Stations	-	-	Future	European
LIFE CARBON FARMING	Development and implementation of a result-based funding mechanism for carbon farming in EU mixed crop livestock systems	https://www.life-carbon-farming.eu/	On-going	European
FAIRSHARE	There is a major focus on digitisation by EU and national/regional policymakers to ensure that digital innovation in agriculture keeps pace with other sectors and the benefits of digitisation are available to the wider farming community. FAIRSHARE will engage, enable and empower the independent farm advisor community, through sharing of tools, expertise and motivations.	https://www.h2020fairshare.eu/	On-going	European
Circular Agronomics	Circular Agronomics (CA) provides a comprehensive synthesis of practical solutions to improve the current Carbon (C), Nitrogen (N) and Phosphorus (P) cycling in European agro-ecosystems and related up- and down-stream processes within the value-chain of food production.	https://www.circularagronomics.eu/	On-going	European

WaterLands	WaterLANDS aims to enable an upscaling of the restoration of wetlands. Socio-economic factors, insufficient stakeholder engagement, lack of government commitment, lack of funding and inadequate exchange of knowledge of restoration methods have all been identified as barriers to successful restoration.	https://waterlands.eu/	On-going	European
Agrilink	The goal of AgriLink is to stimulate transitions towards more sustainable European agricultures by a) furthering the understanding of the roles played by a wide range of advisory organisations in farmer decision-making and b) enhancing their contribution to learning and innovation.	https://www6.inrae.fr/agriiink/	Past	European
Agroecology Transect	Agroecology-TRANSECT aims to contribute to releasing the full potential of agroecology for European agriculture by strengthening the knowledge base for farmers and advisors and supporting decision makers. It aims to deliver robust evidence of the benefits of agroecology on climate change mitigation, biodiversity and farm socio-economic resilience. Agroecology-TRANSECT will: i) deliver a tool to better quantify benefits of agroecology for climate, biodiversity and farm resilience; ii) identify drivers, barriers - including social norms - opportunities and solutions to enhance adoption of agroecological principles; and, iii) launch a toolbox to deliver pragmatic recommendations for the implementation and expansion of agroecological practices by farmers, advisors, policy makers and other actors along the value chain.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060816	On-going	European
NATI00NS	NATI00NS contributes to the Soil Mission objectives by mobilising potential applicants for regional soil health Living Labs open calls funded by the Mission through diverse events whose main results will be reported back to provide policy recommendations and inputs for potential future calls	https://nati00ns.eu/	On-going	European
Contracts2.0	The main objective of Contracts2.0 is to develop novel contract-based approaches to incentivise farmers for the increased provision of environmental public goods. Public goods are non-rival (they cannot be exhausted) and non-excludable (there are no boundaries). An environmental example in the Contracts2.0 context is an open and beautiful landscape which can be enjoyed by one person without... More along with private goods are the objects from ecosystems that people value through experience, use or consumption, whether that value is expressed in economic, social or personal terms. Note that the use of this term here goes well beyond a narrow definit... More. Newly developed contract-based approaches should be environmentally effective, economically viable for farmers and support the longevity of contractual arrangements. Contracts2.0 will investigate the following contract-based approaches: Results-based and collective agri-environmental schemes, Land tenure-based approaches and Value chain approaches.	https://www.project-contracts20.eu/	Past	European
ENFASYS	The EU-funded ENFASYS project aims to better understand lock-ins and levers in farming and food systems, as well as factors stemming from the behaviour of farmers, consumers, and other food chain stakeholders. The project will design policy mixes, business strategies, and social innovations that encourage farmers to transform their production systems.	https://www.enfasysproject.eu/	On-going	European
Roads4Schemes	Road4Schemes will (1) assess the strengths and weaknesses of existing and planned schemes for carbon farming and additional Ecosystem Service (ESS) payments, including respective tools for monitoring, reporting and verification; (2) assess stakeholders' perceptions and preferences with respect to strategies for scheme design and policy drivers and barriers; and (3) deliver a roadmap for developing and implementing contextually sensitive result-based schemes for carbon farming and additional ESS payments.	https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/road4schemes	On-going	European

SoilValues	SoilValues will contribute to the development of successful soil health business models across the EU to improve soil quality and provide land managers with the necessary incentives.	https://soilvalues.eu/	On-going	European
AgriCaptureCO2	AgriCaptureCO2 is developing an innovative, robust, and scalable solution to measure carbon capture in soil.	https://agricaptureco2.eu/why-agricaptureco2e2%82%82/	On-going	European
Agreen	The project “Cross-Border Alliance for Climate-Smart and Green Agriculture in the Black Sea Basin” /AGREEN/ aims to build capacities for networking and transnational knowledge-transfer base in order to escalate the drive for establishing climate-smart farming and maintaining higher rates of economical and social fulfilment as it is the evolution and future.	https://agreen-project.eu/	Past	European
EURAKNOS	EURAKNOS wants to reinforce the EU agricultural knowledge base by building the blueprint for a datasystem to enable the farming/rural community easier access to best practices from all EU H2020 Thematic Networks.	https://euraknos.eu/about	Past	European
LIFE Carbon Dairy	The main aim of the LIFE CARBON DAIRY project was to raise awareness among all stakeholders and promote an approach that would enable dairy production to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions by 20% over 10 years. The project involved 6 regions across France, accounting for 65% of national milk deliveries.	https://idele.fr/carbon-dairy/	Past	National
LIFE Beef Carbon	The LIFE BEEF CARBON project aimed to promote innovative livestock farming systems and associated practices to ensure the technical, economic, environmental and social sustainability of beef farms. Project partners intended to raise awareness among beef production actors and encourage their commitment to improving environmental performance.	https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/index.cfm?fuseaction=search.dspPage&n_proj_id=5355	Past	European
LIFE Green Sheep	The challenges of the LIFE GREEN SHEEP project, which objective is to reduce the carbon footprint of sheep meat and sheep milk by 12% within 10 years, while ensuring the farms’ sustainability, in 5 countries (France, Ireland, Italy, Romania and Spain).	https://life-green-sheep.eu/about-the-project/	On-going	European
iSAGE	The aim of iSAGE is to better characterize the spatio-temporal variability of the albedo of grasslands in France, by measurements carried out in experimental farms and by optical satellite and high-resolution radar, for different grassland management methods and pedo-climatic situations.	https://www.isage.eu/	Past	European
LiveAdapt	LIFE LiveAdapt is part of the LIFE programme of the European Union, in which a multidisciplinary team of entities from Spain, Portugal and France will identify and assess, for four years (2018-2022), solutions for the adaptation to climate change of extensive livestock production models in southern Europe.	https://liveadapt.eu/en/project/what-is-the-life-liveadapt-project/	On-going	European
HyPErFarm	HyPErFarm joins multiple types of actors with the objective to optimize viable agrivoltaic business models as well as test the marketability of the products, via inclusion of new innovative PV technologies (PV H2- production, bifacial PV-panels), radically new crop production systems, stakeholder innovation workshops, and citizen-consumer acceptance, public perception analysis and farmer adoption studies.	https://hyperfarm.eu/about/	On-going	European

The Greefa	The overall concept underpinning the project is based on an innovative use of absorption processes in the greenhouse air-conditioning (also referred as sorptive air conditioning).	https://thegreefa.eu/	On-going	European
RES4LIVE	The RES4LIVE project emphasises on the demonstration of the selected technologies in 4 pilot farms in Belgium, Italy, Germany and Greece, for a duration of at least 12 months, to serve as the means of de-fossilising evidence and impact generation. The overall objective is to provide advanced and cost-effective technologies to the livestock sector that ensure the sustainability of the farms' operation, and the superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact.	https://res4live.eu/	On-going	European
AgroFossilFree	The main goal of AgroFossilFree is to create a framework under which critical stakeholders will cooperate to evaluate and promote the currently available FEFTS in EU agriculture. FEFTS refer to the tools that are required to address cleaner and more efficient energy production and use in agriculture.	https://www.agrofossilfree.eu/	On-going	European
Forage4Climate	The LIFE+FORAGE4CLIMATE project aimed to demonstrate that agricultural systems connected to milk production can contribute to climate change mitigation through the adoption of good practices to reduce emissions, maintaining or increasing the carbon stock in soil used to produce forage for ruminants; and the development and dissemination of tools for the evaluation of the carbon stock and GHG emissions.	http://forage4climate.cipa.it/ngcontent.cfm?a_id=14261&tt=t_bt_app1_www&lang=en	Past	National
EcoNutri	The general objective of ECONUTRI is to optimize, validate, and demonstrate nature-based novel solutions adapted into a holistic concept, which contribute to reduction of NO3-N and P leaching, control of N losses through ammonia volatilization, and mitigation of GHG emissions originating from the agricultural sector, including both plant and animal production.	https://econutri-project.eu/	On-going	European
Trans4Num	The objective is to develop and test innovative Nature Based Solutions practices and pathways that contribute to a socio-ecological transformation of existing intensive agriculture systems towards increasingly sustainable nutrient management.	https://trans4num.eu/en/	On-going	International
Fertimanure	FERTIMANURE is a project dedicated to the innovative nutrient recovery from secondary sources for the production of high-added value FERTILISERS from animal MANURE.	https://www.fertimanure.eu/en/	On-going	International
call HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-5: Pilot network of climate-positive organic farms	-	-	Future	European
INNOVAR	InnoVar aims to augment and improve the efficacy and accuracy of European crop variety testing and decision-making, using an integrated approach incorporating genomics, phenomics and machine learning. Historic data will form the foundation of the InnoVar database which will be expanded with new and harmonised data generated from a trial series across Europe.	https://www.h2020innovar.eu/	On-going	European
ROOT2RES	Root2Res: to develop such tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils.	https://root2res.eu/	On-going	European

IPM Decisions	The project gives farmers and advisers the possibility to access a large number of Integrated Pest Management DSS through a pan-European online Platform and an IPM Decisions Network. The latter being a community of users and stakeholders. Each type of user can access the Platform via a tailored 'dashboard', specific to their requirements. The dashboard acts as the user's control panel to collate information and manage DSS applications.	https://www.ipmdecisions.net/	On-going	European
GrAsTech	European cattle farmers are facing increased demand for pasture-based and environmentally friendly products. Although feeding strategies to reduce Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions have been studied intensively, strategies for grazing systems are under-researched. The lack of easy-to-implement technologies for methane measurement with grazing cattle complicates the necessary large-scale studies. The aim of this project is to develop an animal-mounted sensor platform for methane measurement in grazing cattle and validate using established techniques (Respiration chambers, LaserGun and Greenfeed).	https://www.eragas.eu/en/eragas/research-projects/grastech.htm	Past	European
SmartCow	SmartCow integrates key European cattle research infrastructures to promote their coordinated use and development and thereby help the European cattle sector face the challenge of sustainable production. Covering all the relevant scientific fields and the diversity of cattle types and production systems, SmartCow will provide the academic and private research communities with easy access to high quality services and resources.	https://www.smartcow.eu/	Past	European
LegValue	The objectives of LEGVALUE are; to define platforms for change that can help deliver greater EU self-sufficiency in vegetable protein production; to identify opportunities for innovation, adding value to markets and all participants in the value chains and; to recognise opportunities to influence change, be they at commercial, research or at policy level. The ultimate benefits are the fostering of greater, more profitable legume and pulse production in the EU to satisfy a larger more valuable and diverse market to the financial benefit of all in the value chains and to deliver social and environmental benefits to all.	https://www.legvalue.eu/	On-going	European
BOVINE	BOVINE tackled the urgent sustainability challenges faced by beef producers by bringing together beef farmers, farming organisations, advisors and researchers to collectively develop practical innovations that could be implemented on European beef farms.	https://www.bovine-eu.net/	On-going	European
Disarm	The DISARM group aims to bring people together to discuss and share best practices to promote and sustain responsible use of antibiotics. Any solutions must be effective, practical to use on commercial farms, maintain or improve animal welfare, and carry a cost-benefit to sustain farm economic performance.	https://disarmproject.eu/	Past	European
4D4F	The Data Driven Dairy Decisions for Farmers (4D4F) thematic network will focus on the role which dairy animal and environmental sensors can play in collecting real time information to help make more informed decisions in dairy farming. The network will develop a Community of Practice (COP) comprised of farmers, farm advisors, technology suppliers, veterinarians and researchers who work together to debate, collect and facilitate the co-creation of best practice on data and sensor technology.	https://www.4d4f.eu/	Past	European

NovaSoil	The general objective of NOVASOIL project is highlight the benefits for the society and the environment from the investment in soil health. The main expected outcome of the project is a toolbox for the analysis of suitability of different business cases that promote soil health. This toolbox will be based on a set of good examples from Europe and other countries and the needs and demands from the society.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101091099	On-going	European
InBestSoils	The objective of InBestSoil is to co-create a framework for investment in conservation and recovery of soil health, by developing an economic valuation system of the ecosystem services delivered by a healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives.	https://novasoil-project.eu/	On-going	European
Credible		-	Future	European
ALFA	The overall objective of the ALFA project is to tap the potential of biogas production from livestock farming to enhance the wider uptake of Renewable Energy Systems and increase the share of bioenergy as a baseload energy source, while ensuring reduced emissions from untreated animals' manure and supporting the creation of new jobs and revenue for the livestock farming industry.	https://www.europeanbio gas.eu/project/alfa/	On-going	European
BIOMETHAVERS E	BIOMETHAVERSE aims to diversify the technology basis for biomethane production in Europe, to increase its cost-effectiveness, and to contribute to the uptake of biomethane technologies. To this aim five innovative biomethane production pathways will be demonstrated in five European countries: France, Greece, Italy, Sweden, and Ukraine.	https://www.europeanbio gas.eu/project/biomethaverse/#:~:text=Project%20duration%3A%201%20October%202022,the%20uptake%20of%20biomethane%20technologies_	On-going	European
Sustainable Biogas	The project will improve nutrient management in biogas production by developing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable management practices in Southwest Finland, in Latvia's Zemgale and in Åland Islands • Quality systems for biogas digestate to support market creation in Finland and Latvia • National strategies the for the management of wastewater-based biomasses • National and BSR-wide policy recommendations 	https://sustainablebiogas.eu/	Past	European
Grazing4Agroecology	Grazing4AgroEcology (G4AE) aims to restore farmer confidence and that of the agricultural industry in the production performance and competitiveness of grazing by promoting agroecological innovations for sustainable grazing management. G4AE directly support some of the EU Green Deal objectives: biodiversity restoration, reduction of nutrient losses and reduction of GHG emissions.	https://grazing4agroecology.eu/	On-going	European
ClimateFitFarming	"Holistic Resource Management for Climate Resilience of Farming" – short ClimateFarming – is an Erasmus+ project co-funded by the EU that aims to equip a new generation of farmers, consultants and trainers with skills and knowledge to implement and support climate adaptation and mitigation measures in farming.	http://climatefitfarming.eu/home/	On-going	European

SOLMACC	The project responds to one of the most urgent environmental problems of our time – climate change. The effects of global warming are already making farming more challenging due to the increasing divergence of weather patterns and extreme climatic events. The other side of the coin is that agriculture is currently responsible for about 10% of the total Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the EU. SOLMACC can contribute to proactively confronting these issues by applying a range of optimised farming practices to help make farms more resilient to the effects of climate change and at the same time protecting the environment from harmful greenhouse gases.	https://solmacc.eu/	Past	European
ICaRE4Farms (I4F)	ICaRE4Farms (I4F) intends to boost the use of solar thermal energy (STE) in farming in NWE, to contribute to reduce GHG emissions and increase the share of renewable energies, to help the transition to a low-carbon economy and meet the EU 2030 goal of 27% share for RE. STE is an affordable RE to heat water and has a huge potential to replace fossil energies.	https://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/icare4farms-increase-the-capacity-of-renewable-energies-re-in-farms-in-the-north-west-europe-region-by-using-solar-thermal-energy/	Past	International
LIFE DairyClim	The main objectives of the LIFE-DairyClim project were: 1) to contribute to the mitigation of climate impacts and to decrease GHG emissions in dairy farms, by optimising feeding strategies both in winter (barn feeding) and in summer (grazing and supplementary feeding). In a second step, to implement the selected strategies in pilot farms in Luxembourg, Denmark and Belgium; 2) to contribute to the conservation of grasslands by highlighting their importance for dairy farming and as a potential carbon sink; and 3) to disseminate the outcomes of the project by publications on the project website and writing of guidelines and handbook, including recommendations on agricultural good practices, to ensure transferability of the project results. Substantial reduction in climate impact and GHG emissions of the dairy sector were expected at the end of the project.	https://www.dairyclim.uliege.be/cms/c_5123163/en/dairyclim	Past	International
LIFE Clim'Foot	Clim'Foot set out to support the implementation of public policies that will give public and private organisations incentives to calculate and reduce their carbon emissions. The Clim'Foot project developed common training materials and tools, including a database of emission factors.	https://www.climfoot-project.eu/	Past	European
AGRO MIX	Brings together farmers, researchers and policymakers to explore agroecological solutions for more resilient land use in Europe, developing tools to implement these practices.	https://agromixproject.eu/	On-going	European
CarboSeq	To estimate the feasible SOCsequestration potential taking into account technical and socio-economic constraints	https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq	On-going	European
STEROPES	To overcome the limitations of static soil maps by putting the use of satellite time series forward, test their potential to predict cropland soil organic carbon content over various pedoclimatic conditions and cropping systems across Europe.	https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/steropes	On-going	European

Benchmarks	BENCHMARKS consortium will co-design an Integrated Soil Health Monitoring Framework. This framework will build upon the assessment of soil-based ecosystem functions to co-develop an interactive soil health dashboard for (1) the selection of appropriate soil health indicators, (2) soil health assessment and indexation, and (3) recommendation of management practices to support soil health.	https://soilhealthbenchmarks.eu/about-us/	On-going	Internationa
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List of Flagship Initiatives identified:

Annex 2 - List of flagship initiatives identified.

Flagship Initiatives			
Full Name	Stage	Geography-level	Website
4p1000 initiative	On-going	International	https://4p1000.org/?lang=en
Partnership on agroecology living lab and research infrastructures	On-going	European	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas/ecological-approaches-and-organic-farming/partnership-agroecology_en
Climate - KIC	On-going	European	https://www.climate-kic.org/
European Observatory of Carbon Neutrality	On-going	European	https://climateobservatory.eu/
EU CAP Network	On-going	European	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/index_en
European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management	On-going	European	https://ejpsoil.eu/about-ejp-soil
Global network of lighthouse farms	On-going	International	https://www.lighthousefarmnetwork.com/about-us
Global Research Alliance - Circular Food Systems	On-going	International	https://globalresearchalliance.org/research/integrative-networks/circular-food-systems-network/
Global Research Alliance - Farm to Regional scale integration network	On-going	International	https://globalresearchalliance.org/research/integrative-networks/farm-to-regional-integration-network/
Global Research Alliance - Soil Carbon Sequestration	On-going	International	https://globalresearchalliance.org/research/integrative-networks/soil-carbon-sequestration-network/
Joint Programme Initiative - Climate	On-going	European	https://jpi-climate.eu/
Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change	On-going	European	FACCE-JPI Home - FACCE-JPI (faccejpi.net)
Joint Programme Initiative - Water	On-going	European	http://www.waterjpi.eu/
Mission Adaptation to Climate Change: support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030	On-going	European	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/adaptation-climate-change_en
A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils	On-going	European	https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/soil-health-and-food_en
Standing Committee on Agricultural Research's Strategic Working Group on Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems	On-going	European	https://scar-europe.org/akis-mission-and-aims

List of policymakers identified in the DG Agricultural and Rural Development:

Annex 3 - List of identified policymakers within the DG CLIMA - EU Commission.

DG AGRI		
Code	Unit	Role
DG AGRI 1	AGRI C1: CAP strategic Plans I coordination	Head of unit
DG AGRI 2		Agricultural economics, Policy analysis, Agricultural trade, Bioeconomy
DG AGRI 3	AGRI A: Strategy & Policy Analysis	Policy Officer
DG AGRI 4	AGRI C: CAP strategic Plans I	Policy Officer
DG AGRI 5	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability	Head of Unit: Environmental Sustainability
DG AGRI 6	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability	
DG AGRI 7		Policy Officer - Support the implementation of the EIP AGRI.
DG AGRI 8		Policy Officer
DG AGRI 9	AGRI D: CAP strategic Plans II	
DG AGRI 10	AGRI B1: Economic Sustainability	Acting Director sustainability/ Head of Unit economic sustainability
DG AGRI 11	AGRI B: Sustainability AGRI C: CAP strategic plans I AGRI D:CAP strategic plans II	Policy Officer
DG AGRI 12	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability	Policy officer
DG AGRI 13	AGRI E1: Markets - governance of the agri-food markets	Policy Officer
DG AGRI 14	AGRI E: Markets	Policy Officer
DG AGRI 15	Director-general	

List of policymakers identified in the DG Climate Action:

Annex 4 - List of identified policymakers within the DG CLIMA - EU Commission.

DG CLIMA		
Code	Unit	Role
DG CLIMA 1	CLIMA C3: Innovation for a low carbon, resilient economy	Director innovation for a low carbon, resilient economy
DG CLIMA 2	CLIMA B: Carbon markets and clean mobility	Director carbon markets and clean mobility
DG CLIMA 3	CLIMA C3: Land Economy and Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming	Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals, Directorate-General for Climate Action, European Commission: Land Use, Land Use Change + Forestry, Agriculture, Sustainable Carbon Cycles, Carbon Removal Certification
DG CLIMA 4	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability Policy Officer Environment, climate change, forestry and bioeconomy
DG CLIMA 5	CLIMA E1: Adaptation and resilience to climate change	Head of Unit - Adaptation and resilience to climate change
DG CLIMA 6	CLIMA E: adaptation & resilience, communication and civil society relations	Director adaptation & resilience, communication and civil society relations
DG CLIMA 7	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability	AGRI B2: Environmental Sustainability
DG CLIMA 8	CLIMA C.ADV 01	Advisor innovation for a low carbon, resilient economy
DG CLIMA 9	CLIMA.C.CINEA.C.1	Horizon Europe Climate
DG CLIMA 10	CLIMA C3: Land Economy and Carbon Removals, Carbon Farming	Unit Low Carbon Solutions (III): Land Economy and Carbon Removals

List of policymakers identified in the DG Energy

Annex 5 - List of identified policymakers within the DG ENERGY - EU Commission.

DG ENERGY		
Role	Unit	Role
DG ENERGY 1	ENER C1: Decarbonisation and sustainability of Energy Resources	Head of Unit 'Decarbonisation and sustainability of energy sources'
DG ENERGY 2	ENER C2: Renewables and Energy System Integration Policy	Policy Officer, Renewables and Energy System Integration Policy Unit (ENER.C.1)

List of policymakers identified in the DG Environment

Annex 6 - List of identified policymakers within the DG ENVI - EU Commission.

DG ENVI		
Code	Unit	Role
DG ENVI 1	ENV F: green diplomacy & multilateralism	Director green diplomacy & multilateralism
DG ENVI 2	ENV D.2: Natural capital & ecosystems health	HoU natural capital & ecosystems health
DG ENVI 3	ENV A: General affairs, knowledge and resources	Director general affairs, knowledge and resources
DG ENVI 4	ENV D: Biodiversity	Director Biodiversity
DG ENVI 5	ENV D.1: Land use and management	Head of Unit Land Use and Management
DG ENVI 6	ENV D.3: Nature conservation	Head of Unit nature conservation
DG ENVI 7	ENV C: Zero pollution	Director zero pollution

List of policymakers identified in the DG Research and Innovation

Annex 7 - List of identified policymakers within the DG RTD - EU Commission.

DG RTD		
Code	Unit	Role
DG RTD 1	C2: Bioeconomy and food systems	Policy Officer
DG RTD 2	C2: Bioeconomy and food systems	Head of sector

List of policymakers identified in the Agricultural Committee

Annex 8 - List of the identified policymakers in the AGRI Committee of the EU Parliament.

AGRI Committee	
Code	Role
Agri Committee 1	Rapporteur for opinion on a long-term vision for the EU's rural areas – towards stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous rural areas by 2040
Agri Committee 2	Shadow rapporteur CAP 2021-2027
Agri Committee 3	Vice-chair AGRI/ opinion farm to fork
Agri Committee 4	Member of the European Parliament Committee on Agriculture and Rural Development (AGRI).
Agri Committee 5	Member of the European Parliament Committee on Agriculture and Rural Development (AGRI).
Agri Committee 6	Agri Substitute shadow rapporteur LULUCF
Agri Committee 7	Vice-chair AGRI committee
Agri Committee 8	Rapporteur CAP 2021-2027
Agri Committee 9	Shadow rapporteur CAP 2021-2027
Agri Committee 10	Agri Substitute shadow rapporteur LULUCF
Agri Committee 11	Shadow rapporteur CAP strategic plan
Agri Committee 12	Rapporteur Proposal for a regulation on the labelling of organic pet food/ shadow rapporteur report on sustainable carbon cycles
Agri Committee 13	Rapporteur for the AGRI Opinion Carbon Removal Certification Framework/ shadow rapporteur CAP strategic plans
Agri Committee 14	Chair AGRI committee/ Rapporteur for opinion LULUCF
Agri Committee 15	Rapporteur CAP strategic plan
Agri Committee 16	Rapporteur Common agricultural policy (CAP): financing, management and monitoring 2021–2027

List of policymakers identified in the Environment Committee

Annex 9 - List of the identified policymakers in the Environment Committee of the EU Parliament.

ENVI Committee	
Code	Role
ENVI Committee 1	Vice-chair ENVI committee
ENVI Committee 2	Shadow rapporteur LULUCF
ENVI Committee 3	Shadow rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 4	Rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 5	Rapporteur European Climate Law
ENVI Committee 6	ENVI Substitute shadow rapporteur LULUCF
ENVI Committee 7	CRCF Rapporteur in the ENVI Committee
ENVI Committee 8	Shadow rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 9	Shadow rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 10	Shadow rapporteur LULUCF
ENVI Committee 11	Chair ENVI committee
ENVI Committee 12	Shadow rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 13	Shadow rapporteur Effort Sharing Regulation
ENVI Committee 14	Rapporteur LULUCF

List of policymakers identified in the EU Council

Annex 10 - List of the identified policymakers in the EU Council.

Code	Function /Topic	Country
EU Council 1	Head of Unit - Agriculture, regions and tourism	Austria
EU Council 2	carbon farming, agriculture, regions and tourism	Austria
EU Council 3	Head of Unit climate action, environment, energy, mobility, innovation and technology	Austria
EU Council 4	Attaché Agriculture/carbon farming	Belgium
EU Council 5	Attaché LULUCF	Belgium
EU Council 6	Attaché Climate, Green Deal, biodiversity.	Belgium
EU Council 7	Counsellor, Water management, Horizontal and Global Environmental Issues	Bulgaria
EU Council 8	Environment; Second Secretary Climate Change	Bulgaria
EU Council 9	Agriculture and Fisheries; Head of sector Agriculture and fishery	Bulgaria
EU Council 10	Coordination of the Environment Team	Croatia
EU Council 11	Attaché (Environment, Climate Change)	Cyprus
EU Council 12	Agriculture; counsellor	Cyprus
EU Council 13	Water, soil, nature, biodiversity and environmental impacts	Czech Republic
EU Council 14	Head of Unit Agriculture and Environment Unit	Czech Republic
EU Council 15	Environment Attaché (Nature and Biodiversity, forest, water/sea, sustainable development)	Denmark
EU Council 16	Climate Attaché (Climate Policy)	Denmark
EU Council 17	Counsellor	Estonia
EU Council 18	Counsellor	Estonia
EU Council 19	Senior Specialist	Finland
EU Council 20	Senior Specialist	Finland
EU Council 21	Councillor	France
EU Council 22	Agriculture and Fisheries - Deputy Delegate for Agricultural Affairs, Rural Development, Quality and Organic Farming.	France
EU Council 23	Head of Agriculture Unit	Germany
EU Council 24	Carbon farming	Germany
EU Council 25	Agricultural attaché	Greece
EU Council 26	Agriculture and Environment Policy - Environment attaché	Hungary
EU Council 27	Agriculture and Environment Policy - Green Deal attaché	Hungary
EU Council 28	Attaché, Environment, Biodiversity, Heritage	Ireland
EU Council 29	Executive Officer; General Agricultural Affairs, SCA	Ireland
EU Council 30	Environment and Climate coordinator	Italy
EU Council 31	Agriculture	Italy
EU Council 32	Counsellor Environmental Affairs	Latvia
EU Council 33	Counsellor	Latvia
EU Council 34	Attaché	Lithuania

List of national policymakers identified by NCs

Annex 11 - List of national policymakers identified by NCs.

Code	Organization	Country
National policymaker 1	Agricultural Innovation and Knowledge at Flemish Government	Belgium
National policymaker 2	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries Flanders	Belgium
National policymaker 3	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries Flanders	Belgium
National policymaker 4	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries Flanders	Belgium
National policymaker 5	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries Flanders	Belgium
National policymaker 6	Department of Agriculture and Fisheries Flanders	Belgium
National policymaker 7	Vlaamse Overheid	Belgium
National policymaker 8	Vlaamse Overheid	Belgium
National policymaker 9	Vlaams Energie- en Klimaatagentschap	Belgium
National policymaker 10	Service Public de Wallonie	Belgium
National policymaker 11	Walloon Agency Air Climate	Belgium
National policymaker 12	Walloon Minister for the Environment, Nature, Forestry, Rural Affairs and Animal Welfare	Belgium
National policymaker 13	Walloon Minister for Climate, Energy, Mobility and Infrastructure	Belgium
National policymaker 14	Walloon Minister for the Economy, Foreign Trade, Research and Innovation, Digital, Agriculture, Regional Planning, IFAPME and Skills Centres Dpt. of Clean Air and Industrial Sustainability	Belgium
National policymaker 15	Ministry of Agriculture Directorate for Professional Support to the Development of Agriculture	Croatia
National policymaker 16	Ministry of Agriculture	Croatia
National policymaker 17	Ministry of climate, energy and supply chain, Moderaterne	Denmark
National policymaker 18	Alternativet	Denmark
National policymaker 19	Ministry of agriculture, Venstre Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	Denmark
National policymaker 20	Estonian Farmers Association	Estonia
National policymaker 21	Ministry of Rural Affairs	Estonia
National policymaker 22	Ministry of Rural Affairs	Estonia
National policymaker 23	Producers Cooperative KEVILI	Estonia
National policymaker 24	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Finland
National policymaker 25	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Finland
National policymaker 26	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Finland
National policymaker 27	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Finland
National policymaker 28	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	Finland
National policymaker 29	Ministry of Environment	Finland
National policymaker 30	Ministère de l'Agriculture (DGER et DGPE)	France
National policymaker 31	Ministère de la Transition écologique et de la Cohésion des territoires (CDGG et DGEC)	France
National policymaker 32	CDU- Landtag Niedersachsen	Germany
National policymaker 33	Bündnis 90/Die Grünen	Germany

National policymaker 34	Department for Agricultural Digitisation	Hungary
National policymaker 35	National Agricultural Advisory Committee	Hungary
National policymaker 36	Minister of Agriculture	Hungary
National policymaker 37	Environmental Protection Agency	Ireland
National policymaker 38	Department of Agriculture Food and the Marine	Ireland
National policymaker 39	Department of Agriculture Food and the Marine	Ireland
National policymaker 40	Department of Agriculture Food and the Marine	Ireland
National policymaker 41	Department of Agriculture Food and the Marine	Ireland
National policymaker 42	Teagasc	Ireland
National policymaker 43	Bordbia	Ireland
National policymaker 44	Bordbia	Ireland
National policymaker 45	Teagasc	Ireland
National policymaker 46	Italian National Rural Network	Italy
National policymaker 47	Department of European and International Policies and Rural Development of the Ministry of Agriculture	Italy
National policymaker 48	Ministry of Environment	Italy
National policymaker 49	National CAP Network Unit, EIP Innovation Support Unit and AKIS Coordination Body	Latvia
National policymaker 50	Ministry of Agriculture	Latvia
National policymaker 51	Ministry of Agriculture	Latvia
National policymaker 52	ASTA Administration of technical services in Agriculture	Luxembourg
National policymaker 53	SER Rural Economy Services	Luxembourg
National policymaker 54	ASTA Administration of technical services in Agriculture	Luxembourg
National policymaker 55	Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality	Netherlands
National policymaker 56	Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality Strategy Knowledge and Innovation	Netherlands
National policymaker 57	Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality	Netherlands
National policymaker 58	Portuguese National Rural Network	Portugal
National policymaker 59	Policies and Planning Cabinet of the Ministry of Agriculture	Portugal
National policymaker 60	Environmental Agency	Portugal
National policymaker 61	Food and Veterinary of the Ministry of Agriculture	Portugal
National policymaker 62	Deputy general director of managing authority	Slovakia
National policymaker 63	AKIS Coordination Body	Slovakia
National policymaker 64	Ministry of agriculture, forestry and food (different directorates and national rural network) Institute for preservation and protection of nature	Slovenia
National policymaker 65	Slovenian Ministry for Environment National committee for Agriculture	Slovenia
National policymaker 66	Slovenian Parliament	Slovenia
National policymaker 67	Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic challenge Dpt. of Clean Air and Industrial Sustainability	Spain
National policymaker 68	Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic challenge	Spain
National policymaker 69	Spanish Office for Climate Change, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic challenge	Spain

National policymaker 70	Spanish Office for Climate Change, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic challenge Animal Husbandry Production	Spain
National policymaker 71	Ministry of Agriculture Animal Husbandry Production	Spain
National policymaker 72	Ministry of Agriculture Department of Agriculture	Spain
National policymaker 73	Regional Government of Andalusia	Spain
National policymaker 74	Regional Government of Navarra	Spain
National policymaker 75	Swedish Board of Agriculture	Sweden
National policymaker 76	RUS - Regional development and collaboration in the work with Sweden's environmental goals	Sweden
National policymaker 77	Ministry of Rural Affairs and Infrastructure	Sweden
National policymaker 78	Greppa Näringen	Sweden
National policymaker 79	Federal office for agriculture: Different directorates National Rural Network	Switzerland
National policymaker 80	Environment Agency	UK
National policymaker 81	Defra	UK
National policymaker 82	Defra	UK
National policymaker 83	Natural England	UK
National policymaker 84	NFU	UK
National policymaker 85	Climate Change Committee	UK
National policymaker 86	Country Landowners Association	UK
National policymaker 87	Defra (UK department of environment, food & rural affairs)	UK

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